



Fig. 5. Histograms of the distribution of particles of metals: W, Ti and V deposited on glass plates. Metal foils were irradiated with 5 pulses of argon plasma (W, Ti) and nitrogen plasma (V). Foil thickness: W – 0.6 mm; Ti – 0.9 mm; and V – 0.16 mm.